

STIMULATION OF SOCIAL EMOSTIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION

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Abstract: This study aims to describe the stimulation of social emotional development which includes: children's social emotional abilities, how to stimulate social emotional development and how the role of the teacher group B Setia Kindergarten of Baubau. This research uses descriptive method with a qualitative approach. The subjects of the research is the head master and teachers. The setting of the research in Setia Kindergarten of Baubau. The method of Data collection uses observation, interview, documentation. Besed on the data analyse finding of the research show: 1) social emotional abilities, namely children can get along, socialize and communicate with friends and teachers well, cooperate, be patient waiting for their turn, care and help friends who have difficulty doing assignments in class, sharing food and toys, succumbing to friends , happy to play with friends, not easily angry, love each other and enjoy playing together otherwise there are some children who have not been able to work together, waiting for their turn, easily angry, and difficult to play together. 3) method of stimulating social emotional development that is through habituation, developing children's self-confidence, exemplary and playing. This method can stimulate children's social and emotional development optimally. Teachers have a very important role in child development by involving themselves as role models, mentors, facilitators and motivators for children.

Keywords: Social Emotional Stimulation, Early childhood.

INTRODUCTION

Childhood is a period that is so unique and interesting, that it is difficult to imagine that early childhood or childhood are the same as adulthood. However, in medieval Europe, law usually did not distinguish between children's crime and adult crime. According to expert historian Philippe in Santrock (2007: 7) concluded that European society before 1600th did not give any special status to children. Throughout history, philosophers have made deep speculations about the characteristics of children and how they should be raised. The Egyptians, Greeks, ancient Romans had a rich view of child development. Especially in European history, three influential philosophical views describe the child in terms of original sin, tabulahrassa, and natural goodness (innate).

In the view of original sin, which specifically arises during the mid-century, children are seen to be born into this world as evil beings. The goal of caring for children is to provide salvation to remove sins from the life of children. Approaching the end of the 17th century, Tabula Rasa's

view or the blank tablet was triggered by an English philosopher named Jhon Locke. He denied that children were not bad from birth, but like blank paper, Locke believes that childhood experiences determine children's characteristics and development as adults in future.

He advised parents to spent time with their children and help make the good community members and useful. In the 18th century, the innate goodness view was initiated by a French philosopher named Jean Jacques Rosseau. He emphasized that children are basically good. Thus the child should be allowed naturally with little supervision or limitations from parents and care providers in order to develop.

Today, the western view of children states that childhood is a unique and very lively period. The current approach to childhood identifies different periods in which children master certain skills and tasks that prepare them to enter maturity.

Childhood is not seen as an uncomfortable period, where adults tolerate children's ignorance. Instead, we protect children from the pressures and responsibilities of adult work through strict child labor laws. In short, now we assess childhood as a special time for growth and change, and provide extensive resources in the effort of caring for and educating children, so as to be intelligent, good and useful for their environment.

Early childhood education is an effort to provide stimulation of all aspects of its development from the age of 0 to 8 years adjusted to the stages of its development. Early childhood education is divided into two elements, namely through formal and non-formal education. Indonesia as a country that has a lot of ECE in formal form with the aim that all the nation's children get an even education, to develop all the potential of children as a manifestation of the nation's vision in educating the life of the nation.

In other countries early childhood education is the age range 0-8 years based on NAEYC (Morrison, 1988: 4) early childhood is a child from birth to 8 years old. Indonesia early childhood is a group of people aged 0-6 years based on Law Number 20 of 2003 years concerning the National Education System states that early childhood education is a coaching effort that is shown to children from birth to six years of age which is carried out through the provision of educational stimulation to help growth physical and spiritual development so that children have readiness to enter education in the future.

Early childhood is a period that is very sensitive to get information in their environment. At this age the child has an intellectual capacity of 80%. It means that the child has a strong catching power against the information obtained. Maria Montessor (1995) , an early child, called it Absorbent Mind a fast-absorbing thought. Information that enters through the child's senses is quickly absorbed into the brain. The absorption capacity of a child's brain can be likened to a sponge that quickly absorbs water. For this reason educators should not be wrong in giving concepts to children.

One aspect of early childhood development that needs to be considered by educators and parents is social and emotional children. According to Ary Ginanjar (2007) one intelligence that must be possessed by children is EQ (Emotional Question). A person's ability to socialize and adapt is based on emotional ability, so educators and parents have an important role in stimulating children's social emotional development.

Today many of the phenomenon that are very concerned in our community as broadcast of the Metro TV program broadcasts on Friday, July 20, 2018 "The Rise of Drug Abusers Under Age", on the other hand there are also many underage sexual abuse. This phenomenon is caused by a lack of education that is maximal in the family and school environment. Therefore educators and parents should be good examples and wise educators.

Kihadjar Dewantoro (Sudjiono, 2009: 126) said that teachers and parents in providing education to their sons and daughters must have 3 concepts namely; *Ingarso sung tulodo*, meaning that teachers and parents are role models or role models for their children. *Ingmadyo mangun karso*, as well as a mentor in teaching and *Tut wury handayani*, teachers and parents always provide motivation and encouragement to encourage children to develop their potential. Education can be obtained from several elements, namely education through family, community and school environment. These three components have a very important role in influencing changes and development of children.

While the research finding of Giacomo et al's reserach (2013: 1978), concluded that the development of social emotional aspects in the development of children including developing self-regulation, self-control, social ability, and building a harmonious relationship between peers . It can develop various aspects of child development including cognitive aspects, behavior, and social emotional abilities.

Based on theories and concepts and field phenomena researchers are called above to conduct research with the title Stimulation of the aspects social emotional development at group B Setia Kindergarten of Baubau to obtain information on good stimulation steps to be applied to other schools.

This study aims to describe and analyze social emotional abilities, methods of stimulating social emotional development and the role of teachers in early childhood education in Setia kindergarten of Baubau.

Literature Review

The Concept of AUD

Early childhood is a child aged 0 to 8 years. Children at this age are a critical development period or referred to as the golden age. According to NAEYC (Morrison, 1988: 4) early childhood is a child from birth to 8 years old. At this age the child has 80% potential to absorb information from the environment.

While Suyanto (2005: 1) referred to as early childhood is a child with ages 0 to 8 years. Children of this age have different characteristics with children in their age. As stated by John Locke (1988: 43) that children can say "the child was born like the blank tablet" means that children are born like blank paper, for the environment children will shape it into a good person. If parents do not give serious attention to child growth and development, then the child will experience delays and obstacles in their growth and development. With the ability of the child to be able to adapt to obtain knowledge and construct it. As stated by Vigostky (Ratus, 2014: 24) views early childhood as an adaptive person who is able to communicate and interact with his social environment. Vygotsky emphasized to educators and parents to understand the concept of ZPD (zone proximally development) and scaffolding. This means that during a child's development there is a very critical or potential period that can be used by parents to develop optimal children's potential with help or support (scaffolding).

Sujiono (2009: 6), explains that early childhood is an individual who is undergoing a process of development rapidly and fundamentally for his life. Early childhood is in the age range 0-8 years. During this time the process of growth and development in various aspects is experiencing a fast period in the span of the development of human life. Stimulation is given as a learning process in developing all aspects of child development, but in giving stimulation to the child must pay attention to the characteristics of child development.

Social Emotional Development

Parke and Alison (2011: 2), explain that social development is a picture of children's social behavior and shows greater change. This relates to children's ideas or thoughts about themselves and others, children's relationships with their peers and adults, children's emotional expressions shown as their social abilities in groups. While Fathi (2012: 1648), explained that children's social abilities are children's skills in completing various activities in their environment and are able to develop emotional ability in interacting with people around them.

Yusuf (2014: 122), social development is defined as a learning process to be able to adjust to norms or group rules, morals, or customs, merge into a unity and communicate with each other and cooperate. The definition is similar to Suyanto (2005: 70), explaining that social development is the ability of children to adapt to their social environment effectively for example children can share, help, courtesy, honestly. A person's ability to socialize is inseparable from the role of good emotional regulation. According to Daniel Golmen (1997) Emotional intelligence (emotion quention plays an important role in one's social development.

Susanto (2011: 135), describes emotional development as a person's inner feelings, both in the form of mental upheaval, lust, mental and physical state that can appear or manifest into forms or symptoms such as fear, anxiety, anger, moodiness, irritation , jealousy, love, affection, and curiosity.

The same definition is explained by Levine and Joyce (2014: 327), that emotion is an experience of fear which is included in the physiological reactions of a person's body, the interpretation of a person in a situation, communication with others and one's actions in responding to it. While Santrock (2014: 282), describes emotional development is a feeling or desire that occurs when someone in an environment can interact. Emotional development is classified into positive and negative emotions. Positive emotions such as happiness, pleasure, love, while negative emotions such as anxiety, anger, doubt, and sadness.

Besed on some of definitions can be concluded that emotional development is a person's feelings both positive and negative for example happy, happy, loving, angry, and sad which results in a physiological reaction which involves a conscious experience and experience that results in a person's behavior in interpreting a situation, communication with others and one's actions in responding to the situation.

Social Emotional Behavior

Hurlock (1980: 116-118), suggested some early childhood social and emotional behavior that would be very visible when children aged 2.5 years to 3.5 and 5.5 years to 6.5 years, involves :

- 1) *Imitating*, children to be the same as certain groups so that the child imitates the attitudes and behavior of the people he admires.
- 2) *Competition*, the desire to surpass and defeat his friend and this behavior will appear at the age of 4 years.
- 3) *Collaboration*, at the end of the year arises when playing koopertif and group activities begin to develop and increase.
- 4) *Sympathy*, sympathy is an understanding of other people's feelings and emotions that will arise at the age of three years, and increases when many children build communication with other children.
- 5) *Empathy*, empathy is a feeling and emotion that is applied really to others but on the other hand also requires the ability to imagine yourself in the position of others.

- 6) *Social support*, towards the end of childhood, support from friends becomes more important than adults. *Dividing*, children to get good experiences with other children so that children will share their belongings with other children such as games or food.
- 7) *Negativism*, against more mature people. This behavior occurs at the age of three years and four years. This negativism is shown by physical resistance.
- 8) *Aggressive*, this behavior is shown at the age of two and four years by verbal attacks or verbal abuse.
- 9) *Behavior*, power or love is shown about three years and tends to increase with increasing contact with other children and usually girls.
- 10) *Thinking about yourself*, children often think of themselves but gradually this behavior will decrease but generous behavior is still very small.
- 11) *Damaging*, an outburst of anger is often accompanied by an act of damaging surrounding objects, regardless of the property of another person or his person.

Based on these explanations it can be interpreted that through interaction with the environment, children can build social behavior patterns that will shape them to easily share and sympathize. However, if the environment gives inconvenience to the child then the thing he shows is aggressive behavior, anger, and physical action.

Early Childhood Emotion Behavior Early

Childhood emotional behavior will appear at the age of 2.5 years to 3.5 and 5.5 years to 6.5 which is indicated by the following emotional behaviors:

- 1) *Anger*, the cause of anger in children is generally caused by quarrels about the game, lack of fulfillment of desires and severe attacks on other children. The child's anger is marked by crying, shouting, bluffing or hitting.
- 2) *Fear*, habituation, imitation, and memory of children about unpleasant experiences that cause fear, such as stories, pictures, radio / television shows, and films with frightening elements, the reactions that will occur in children are shown by hiding even crying.
- 3) *Jealousy*, the child becomes jealous when his parents' attention shifts to others. In families this usually can happen for example to a newborn sister. Children's jealousy can be shown by things like, pretending to be sick, naughty, and wet.
- 4) *Inquiry*, children have a high curiosity about many new things. The first reaction shown by the child is in a sensorimotoric form where it reacts by asking.
- 5) *Envy*, children often show jealousy about the abilities or goods of other children. This jealousy can be demonstrated by complaining about the goods themselves.
- 6) *Happy*, the child feels happy because the situation is fun, for example when the child can do the task, the child's feeling of joy can be shown by clapping, jumping and hugging.
- 7) *Sad*, children feel sad because they lost something they like, both in the form of games and people around them. In particular this sadness is shown by crying.
- 8) *Affection*, children who love pets or objects that are fun are usually shown by hugging the object or kissing certain objects.

Based on the description, it can be interpreted that through the interaction of children with their environment, children can manage their emotional patterns by showing joy. Conversely, if the environment gives inconvenience, what is shown by the child is anger, sadness, and fear.

Stages of Early Childhood Social Emotional Development

Erikson (2010: 291), mentions several stages of children's social emotional development including Trust vs. mistrust, Autonomy vs shame, Initiative vs. Guilt, Industry vs. inferiority, these stages can be explained as follows:

Trust vs Mistrust. At this stage a baby must get love from his mother or caregiver, and must be fulfilled all his physical and emotional needs. If the baby is raised in such an environment, there will be a sense of security and trust in the environment, and will develop healthy emotional development. When the child does not get enough attention, the child will develop mistrust understanding of the people around him and can influence the next developmental stage.

Autonomy vs shame. At this stage, the child feels able to do something and feels unique with all the advantages as an individual. Parents who limit too much and prohibit children's activities will feel embarrassed and doubtful of their abilities. Therefore, both parents and teachers must support children's activities in experimenting and exploring their environment to become versatile.

Initiative vs. Guilt. At this stage the child has the potential to develop in a positive direction. These positive developments include creativity, lots of ideas, imagination, dare to try, dare to take risks, and like to hang out with peers. Positive developments like this depend on conducive learning environment conditions. If parents and educators restrict children to exploring, curiosity and creativity, the child will develop a sense of doubt about his abilities. Therefore, parents and kindergarten educators must encourage and condition these social attitudes and positive emotions so that the child becomes versatile.

Industry vs inferiority. At this time children experience a very critical period to develop their confidence. Children are very enthusiastic to learn and imagine, so that they grow up with an attitude of wanting to work, succeed, be highly motivated, and have a work ethic. If parents and educators do not give confidence to children for creativity, then the child will develop an understanding of inferiority or lack of confidence in their abilities. Thus, parents and educators must support all activities and provide space, as well as various equipment that can build understanding of the child's industry.

Based on the stages of social emotional development, it can be concluded that the social development of children is largely determined by the child's environment in which they are located, both the family environment and peers and the child's motivation to interact to develop their ideas, as well as their imagination to work.

Stimulation of Social Emotional Development

Teachers in early childhood education have a duty to improve and encourage children's social and emotional development. Positive social and emotional development allows children to learn better and succeed in all school activities. During childhood, the child is at the psychosocial stage. while Morrison (2012: 221), explains that there are several ways teachers can do to develop children's emotional social:

- 1) Give the child the freedom to find out
- 2) Give projects with activities that make it easier for children to find and experiment.
- 3) Encourage and support children's efforts to design, make things, and participate in learning about self-regulation and increasing the ability to control their emotions and behavior to build positive social relationships with others.

The teacher's task in teaching self-regulation at school, including:

Give various learning activities.

- 1) Organize the learning environment to help children do their best. For example in the beam game, make sure the activity of building a beam gets enough space and is protected from passing. Avoid settings that invite children to run and fight.
- 2) Know each child well, build relationships with parents, and support children's strengths and their needs.
- 3) Determine clear boundaries regarding unacceptable behavior and plant rational explanations for children in an atmosphere of mutual respect and love.
- 4) Work with children to make simple group rules. Some good rules are taking care of others, taking care of yourself, and maintaining classrooms. Embed this rule for a year.
- 5) Use the language from the child as often as possible. Try to support your culture.
- 6) Train children to convey their feelings verbally and accompany children when children experience problems.
- 7) Example of good self-regulation by talking to yourself.

Santrock (2008: 460), explains that there are several stimuli that can be done by teachers or parents for guidance on children's social emotional development, including:

- 1) Improve children 's self esteem. Can be refined by identifying the causes of low self esteem, providing emotional support and social approval and helping children's achievement.
- 2) Help children understand their emotion and cope with stress. When children can express their emotions stable, try to keep them from feeling stressed, and help children learn effectively strategically.
- 3) Nurture children's moral development. Parents can help their children with warm care rather than punishment, provide discipline and provide opportunities with children to learn about views in the family environment and social behavior.
- 4) Create school that supports children socio emotional development. Teachers not only provide good stimulation of children's cognitive development but also must know how children feel comfortable with themselves.
- 5) Improve childrens 'peer and friend ship skills. Peers and good friendships are very important to improve children's prosocial behavior

The strategy presented was supported by the results of Celene et al. (2007: 82), concluded that the teacher's strategy in educating and caring for effective parents can provide a comprehensive social emotional understanding and increase children's knowledge of emotional, self-regulation, the level of social relations and social skills during preschool.

While the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Regulation No. 137 of 2014 years concerning National Standards for Early Childhood Education stated that the content standards on the level of early childhood development achievement that became the basis of teachers to provide social emotional development of children, are as follows:

Self-awareness

- 1) Shows the ability to adjust to the situation.
- 2) Showing caution to people who are not yet known (growing trust in the right adult).
- 3) Knowing your own feelings and managing them naturally (controlling yourself naturally).

Responsibility

- 1) Know the rights.
- 2) Obey class rules (activities, rules).
- 3) Organize yourself.
- 4) Responsible for his behavior for his own good.

Prosocial behavior

- 1) Play with peers.
- 2) Knowing his friend's feelings and responding naturally.
- 3) Share with others.

While the finding research of Giacomo et al. (2013: 1978), concluded that the development of social emotional aspects in the development of children including developing self-regulation (self regulation), self-control (social control), social ability, and building a harmonious relationship between peers . It can develop various aspects of child development including cognitive aspects, behavior, and emotional social abilities. Thwaites (2008: 75), suggested some stimulation of social emotional development of children aged 5 to 6 years including:

- 1) Develop children's confidence.
- 2) Develop a better child's personality.
- 3) Teach children to have good social skills, such as sharing, helping.
- 4) Encourage children to cooperate in various activities.
- 5) Teach children awareness about rules, and good moral codes.

Based on these theories can be interpreted that the stimulation of social emotional development of early childhood, educators are emphasized to provide learning that is centered on the child and provides freedom for children to explore with their environment. Children can be developed in all aspects of their development through guidance in regulating their emotions, developing self-awareness, responsibility, and good social behavior.

METHODS

This study uses a type of field research with a qualitative approach, namely research methods based on phenomenological philosophy, used to examine the condition of natural objects. In qualitative research, the researcher is a key instrument, data source sampling is done by purposive sampling technique, which aims to obtain data on the seventh subject and found in the field. Collection techniques with triangulation (combined), data analysis are inductive / qualitative, and research results emphasize meaning rather than generalization.

Researcher used qualitative research methods because their research is carried out under natural conditions and considers that social reality as something that is holistic or intact, complex, dynamic, meaningful, and symptomatic relationships are interactive. Research is carried out on natural objects, namely objects that develop as they are, not manipulated by researchers and the presence of researchers does not affect the dynamics of the object. This method is also used to obtain in-depth data, a data that contains meaning (Sugiyono, 2010: 14-15). Thus the researchers will get meaningful data from the application of strategy of stimulating early childhood social emotional development in group B Setia Kindergarten of Baubau city.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Finding

Social Emotional Social Abilities

Social and emotional abilities in early childhood are two different things but influence each other. Social ability is the ability possessed by each individual in building social interaction and being able to adapt to their environment or can also be interpreted as social development is the ability of children to build communication with their environment and gain knowledge about prosocial behavior, and values held in the community. Children are capable of prosocial behavior, namely, sharing, respecting others, responsibility, empathy and collaboration. While emotional ability is one's ability to regulate and control emotions in building cooperative relationships with others.

There are 2 types of emotion in the development of emotion: first positive emotions which include happy behavior, smile, sympathy. both negative emotions which include anger, aggressive, crying and sadness. While emotional development is a feeling or desire that occurs when someone in an environment can interact. Emotional development is classified into positive and negative emotions. Positive emotions such as happiness, pleasure, love, while negative emotions such as anxiety, anger, doubt, and sadness. Children who grow up with good emotions, so the ability to be social can develop optimally. finding of the interview, the group B children in Setia Kindergarten Kindergarten can share food with their friends, but there are also those who have not shared, can empathize, be cheerful when playing together, and there are also children who cry when the game is taken by their friends.

The interview data shows that the social emotional behavior of early childhood in Setia Kindergarten has different characteristics. Setia Kindergarten teachers realize that there are children who can share food, help their friends, queue in play, obey the rules, be cheerful, enjoy playing, and work together, there are also children who cannot share, cannot empathize and cry.

The interview data was strengthened by the results of observations of children of group B in Setia Kindergarten, when eating with children sharing food with friends, washing hands and praying before eating, queuing in play, sitting neatly when eating and some walking while eating, cooperating, caring and helping friends who have difficulty doing assignments in class, and there are still children who are irritable, irritable, caring and helping friends who have difficulty doing assignments in class, sharing food and toys, succumbing to friends, respecting teachers and being responsible.

Based on the finding of interviews and observations, it can be concluded that the social and emotional abilities of children in Setia Baubau Kindergarten are the ability to socialize, socialize and communicate well with friends and teachers, patiently waiting for their turn, others who cannot wait their turn, cooperate, empathy cheerful in playing, loving each other. Children's social skills in Setia Kindergarten of Baubau \are in accordance with the Standard of Child Development Achievement Level social emotional aspects in children aged 4 to 6 years.

Stimulation of Social Emotional Development

Based on finding of interviews and observations in Setia Kindergarten shows that in stimulating emotional social development the teacher uses several strategies namely habituation, developing children's self-confidence, exemplary, teaching children to have good social skills, such as sharing, helping, encouraging children to cooperate in various activities, teaching children

awareness about rules, and good moral codes. The implementation of social emotional development strategies at group B Setia kindergarten of Baubau city, as follows:

Habituation

Based on finding of the interview, this strategy is used in learning activities that aim to foster habits and form a good personality. Emotional social development carried out by habituation, namely: saying and answering greetings, queuing in waiting for their turn, happy to play groups, sharing food, apologizing when doing wrong, eating and drinking in an Islamic way of dressing Muslim / Muslimah, and saying honestly. Through habituation in good social emotional behavior, the child will get used to doing it in everyday life.

The finding of the interviews were also supported by observations showing teachers in Kindergarten Kindly familiarize children to share food when eating, familiarize children to help their friends, queue in waiting for their turn, familiarize children to say politely and behave honestly.

To stimulate children's social emotional development through habituation. Our children in Setia Kindergarten feel good for doing good emotional social behaviors, so that children are accustomed to sharing, empathy, sympathy, playing together, easily regulating their emotions, and helping each other and being responsible. "Habit is one of the right methods to stimulate various aspects of child development. In the concept of habituation is the habit of doing a good deed, namely prosocial sharing, helping, cooperation, playing together, sympathy and being responsible. Such behavior is built with habits to be done in everyday life, so children will become personal who have good social skills.

Based on the finding of interviews and observations, it can be concluded that the teachers in Setia Kindergarten of Baubau developed the social and emotional abilities of children through habituation namely, the teacher familiarizes children to share, helps their friends, queues in waiting for their turn, obeys the rules, accustoms children to give and answer greetings, say honestly, and empathize. Children who are accustomed to good behavior, children will develop these behaviors as adults.

Develop children's confidence

Teachers who always develop children's self-confidence well, the child will develop trust, autonomy, initiative, industry behavior. Children who have high self confidence can develop their potential well; children can build social relationships with their peers, siblings and school environment well. Based on the results of interviews in Setia Kindergarten developing social emotional based on the stages of child development. The teacher develops children's self-confidence with positive support in children's activities and creativity, supports children's play, collaboration, builds good communication between teachers and children so that a good partnership is formed in the teaching and learning process.

The interview data shows that teachers in Setia Kindergarten stimulate social emotional development of children through positive support. Support, strong motivation in guiding children in the learning process and learning are good methods and play an important role. Teachers in Setia Kindergarten always strive to stimulate children properly through positive motivation and support to build high self-confidence in children, we realize social and emotional behavior in Setia Kindergarten there are some children who have not been able to regulate their emotions irritable, crying, there also children who have high motivation and initiative, high self-confidence in completing the assigned tasks, happy to play together and share, not easily angry.

The next interview data shows that the teacher realizes the nature of each child has different characteristics, there are children who have a positive temperament and also negative ones, there are also children who are easily irritable, crying, easily discouraged and there are children who have confidence who are high in creativity, build social relationships. Characteristics of the child are influenced by various factors both from the family environment, school, and peers. The interview data is strengthened by the results of observations when children learn to use "flash cards", the children are very enthusiastic and cooperate with each other, there is one child who asks the teacher, there are also children who have not been able to cooperate with their friends. The results of observations of children show different social and emotional behaviors. There are children who have a sense of self-esteem (self esstem) that is high in building social relationships, playing with friends and dare to ask questions, express ideas and ideas and there are also children who have not been able to express their ideas and ideas.

Based on the finding of interviews and observations it can be concluded that to develop social emotional children can also be stimulated through good support and motivation. Early childhood has a high absorptive capacity so that its behavior is easy to be formed through supportive stimulation, cooperation, motivation in carrying out children's activities, whether it is doing tasks, playing, expressing their ideas and building cooperation. Support will generate enthusiasm and high self-confidence, he will feel he is able and able to do his ideas, so he will be a person who is not easily discouraged, shy and has a high spirit of creativity.

Exemplary

Based on finding of interviews this strategy is used in learning activities that aim to guide children in forming a good personality. Emotional social development carried out by example is the teacher in Setia Kindergarten not only as a teacher but also as an example of both the example of behavior, usage, the discipline of time, and exemplary in polite words. The teacher has a very important role as an example for his students, thus the teacher should be a good example. Children have high memory and have the ability to imitate the behavior and words they hear.

Subsequent interviews show that social emotional development in Setia Kindergarten is through example or as a role model for students, teachers are disciplined to arrive on time, dress discipline, discipline to speak polite and behave well in front of children. The results of the interviews were corroborated by observations that showed that the teacher always arrived on time before the children arrived, prepared learning media, arranged the study room, and guided the children to line up before entering the classroom.

Based on the finding of interviews and observations it can be concluded that the teacher has a very important role in the growth and development of children. In its role the teacher is not only a teacher, but as an example, to create intelligent students has good manners. Teachers as role models are role models for their students whether they are exemplary in dress discipline, time, polite words and good social behavior.

Playing

Prominent characteristic of early childhood is kindergarten (play). Even children from birth need activists to play through interaction with their environment. Playing for a child is an activity that is very important for the growth and development of children. Based on interviews, the teacher motivates children to play together through various types of games, one of which is playing beams, playing rules and playing roles, by playing the roles and rules of children directly involved in

playing characters and characters, so that children absorb the essence of the role of characters Besides that, children also play with rules (game with rule).

Early childhood is a very sensitive period, meaning that children at this age should be for teachers and parents to stimulate children through fun activities and contain good social emotional values. Playing is one of the right methods that can generate motivation, and good collaboration between children.

The same thing was stated in a subsequent interview that one of the social and emotional development of children is playing, be it playing, role playing, playing rules (game with rule), through children's play can build effective social and emotional relationships. The results of the interview are supported by observations that show children love to play puzzles with their friends, want to wait their turn when playing slides and swings.

About 20 percent of children worldwide experience high levels of stress because their playing time is taken. Therapists such as occupational therapists, child life specialists, speech therapists, physical therapists, and many other human service providers use therapeutic games with toys and games to facilitate treatment goals that are appropriate to their discipline. Such games involve children and help prepare them to encourage verbalization, and help develop gross and fine motor skills, and other benefits.

Based on finding of interviews and observations, it can be concluded that playing for early childhood is very appropriate, because this game leads to the formation of self-ability to live independently, choose and act on one's own abilities. role playing can make children's imaginative power, various psychological expressions. Rule play (game with rule) is also in the game model oriented to the development of cooperative skills and children's self-socialization. This game is intended to build a pattern of obeying the rules, and knowing the rules, cooperting, friendship, empathy, sharing, and helping with this game model can develop a high child's spirit.

The Role of Teachers Early Childhoo Education

The teacher has a very important role in the learning process both character building and children's academic development. The teacher is a spearhead for the nation's generation by him, a teacher not only as a teacher, but also as a role model, educator, motivator and mentor for children. The interview finding showed that teachers in the Setia Kindergarten have roles as role models, teachers, motivators, mentors, and facilitators. The teacher as an model, it means that the teacher must be able to be an example for her students through daily activities. The teacher must be able to be an example of discipline to dress, speak words politely, and come to school in a timely manner.

The finding of the interviews were supported by observations that showed the teacher arrived on time before the children arrived, prepared learning media, arranged the study room, and guided the children to line up before entering the classroom.

The finding of the interviews and observations were also supported by the children's learning activities in Setia Kindergarten which showed children could line up with attention to jokes, children, children could dress neatly, and come on time.

Based on finding of interviews, observations and documentation, it can be concluded that teachers have a very important role in the growth and development of children. In its role the teacher is not only as a teacher, but as an example, educator, motivator and mentor to create intelligent students have good manners. Teachers as role models are role models for their students whether they are exemplary in dress discipline, time, polite words and good social behavior. On

the other hand the teacher is also a motivator who provides encouragement and motivation so that children want to learn, share, help others, empathize and behave honestly.

DISCUSSION

Social Emotional Ability

Based on the finding of the research, it is known that the social abilities of children in Setia Baubau Kindergarten include: the ability to get along, socialize and communicate with friends and teachers well, cooperate, be patient waiting for their turn, care and help friends who have difficulty working on assignments class, sharing food and toys, succumbing to friends, happy to play with friends, not easily angry, love each other and enjoy playing together otherwise there are some children who have not been able to cooperate, wait their turn, get angry easily, and are difficult to play together.

Child prosocial behavior in Permendikbud number 137 of 2014 concerning Early Childhood Education Standards includes: 1) ability to play with peers, 2). Understanding feelings, 3) responding, 4). share, 5). respect the rights and opinions of others, 6). cooperative, 7). koleran, and 9). behave politely. Hurlock (1978: 209-249) explains that patterns of social behavior and in early childhood include: imitation, competition, desire to surpass and defeat others, cooperation with peers, sympathy. Empathy, social support, happiness, sadness, love, shame, pleasure, jealousy and sharing (children are willing to share toys, food and so on). Kindergarten as a form of early childhood education services formal channels have an important role to optimize all aspects of child development. Kindergarten can make a positive contribution to children's social emotional development because the kindergarten atmosphere is partly like a family atmosphere; children have the opportunity to actively move, play, and cheerfully all of which have pedagogical values; and children can get along with peers. The function of kindergarten education is to foster, grow, develop all the child's potential optimally so that basic behaviors and abilities are formed according to the stages of development so that they have the readiness to enter further education.

According to Aviles, at al (2006: 38) that children who at school experience emotional social development disorders will experience a decline in academic and at the age of adulthood will experience mental health disorders, where the child will become a human apathy and selfishness. Manisha Goel and Preeti Aggarwal (2012: 89) argue that a person who is confident feels he has mature social and emotional competencies, is quite intellectual, successful, satisfied, assertive, optimistic, independent, confident, moving forward, quite firm and has quality leadership. So the concept of self-confidence enjoys an important position in the theory of behavior and human personality and is considered the basic condition of human existence in the modern world by many thinkers.

Early childhood needs to be given the right stimulation to develop various aspects of child development. Given that early childhood is a child who is in the developmental stage often referred to as the golden age or referred to as the golden age, at this age the intellectual capacity of children is 80% Blooms (Suyadi, 2016). This was confirmed by Maria Montessori (1999: 24) that childhood is a sensitive period or (sensitive period), children are easy to absorb information from their environment. Therefore educators and parents can provide appropriate early stimulation in accordance with the stages of child development.

Stimulation of children's social emotional development.

Based on finding of the research in Setia Kindergarten, showed that the stimulation of children's social emotional development was carried out through several methods, namely silence, developing self-confidence in the children, and playing. The description of the strategy is as follows:

Habituation

This strategy is used in learning activities that aim to foster habits and form a good personality. Emotional social development carried out by habituation, namely: saying and answering greetings, queuing in waiting for their turn, happy to play groups, sharing food, apologizing when doing wrong, eating and drinking in an Islamic way of dressing Muslim / Muslimah, and saying honestly. Through habituation with good behavior, prosocial, the child will grow with a healthy emotional social spirit. Habit is to do something repeatedly. That is to say what the child does in learning is repeated continuously until he can truly understand it and can be embedded in his heart. With a well-planned habituation activity, it certainly affects the results obtained in educating children, so that children can understand and familiarize the activities that have been taught. This method is very good to use because children still like to accept habituations that are applied to themselves and early childhood is not much affected by the outside world.

This strategy of habituation is also carried out at the Insantama Bogor Integrated Islamic Elementary School (SDIT), the method applied has succeeded in getting students from entering the entrance to school. Students get used to positive behavior, so they have noble character, like have character to God (love God), behave whole heartedly, be honest, feel confident, be assertive, forgive, say well, be tolerant, and have character towards the environment by loving nature and keeping the environment clean (Santi Lisnawati, 2016 : 413).

This strategy was coined by Pavlov (Brooks, 2011) called classical conditioning theory. This theory emphasizes for educators to always give repetition of habituation to children from something unknown so that children are able to be independent. This means that if the child is accustomed to good behavior in the school environment and his daily activities, then the child can grow with a healthy social emotional. To stimulate children's social and emotional development through habituation of good social emotional behaviors, so that children are accustomed to sharing, empathizing, sympathizing, playing together, easily regulating their emotions, and helping each other and being responsible. Habit is one of the right methods to stimulate various aspects of child development. In the concept of habituation is the habit of doing a good deed, namely prosocial sharing, helping, cooperation, playing together, sympathy and being responsible. Such behavior is built with habits to be done in everyday life, so children will become personal who have good social skills. Eileen and Cowdery (2012: 310), say that behavioral approaches to stimulate children's social emotionality, namely Every child can learn. In classrooms it is very important to emphasize the principle of "Every child can learn". This means that children are accustomed to learning good behavior in a school environment. The results of this study are supported by research conducted by Malti et al. (2012: 4) shows that children improve their social emotional through habits to share and show good relationships with others in early childhood.

Sharing can be predicted as a child's ability to sympathize with peers who need help and children can interact well with those around them as their social abilities. The results of this study are also supported by Sharma & Sharma (2014: 4), concluding that to develop children's social emotional, which is the main factor is the teacher's ability to guide children with different cultures, develop curricula that are appropriate to environmental conditions, provide various activities in

children, build friendly communication with friends and people around them, familiarize children to respect each other, and behave politely. The teacher will be a guide for children in building harmonious relationships in the school environment. Satomi et al. (2002: 16), concluded that good classroom management, teaching responsibility, and giving rules by teachers can improve children's moral behavior.

Developing the social and emotional abilities of children through habituation namely, the teacher accustoms the child to share, help his friends, queue in waiting for their turn, obey the rules, familiarize the child members and answer greetings, say honestly, and empathize. Children who are accustomed to good behavior, children will develop these behaviors as adults.

Develop Self Confidence

Teachers who always develop children's self-confidence so well, children will develop trust, autonomy, initiative, industry behavior. Children who have high self confidence can develop their potential well; children can build social relationships with their peers, siblings and school environment well. To develop social emotional children can also be stimulated through good support and motivation.

Early childhood has a high absorptive capacity so that its behavior is easy to be formed through supportive stimulation, cooperation, motivation in carrying out children's activities, whether it is doing tasks, playing, expressing their ideas and building cooperation. Support will increase your child's enthusiasm and confidence, he will feel he is able and able to do his ideas, so he will become a person who is not easily discouraged, embarrassed and has a high spirit of creativity. According to Erikson (Morrison, 2012: 82) children's personality and social skills grow and development in the family, school and community environment, thus this institution has an important role in providing support and motivation so that children have high trust and independent spirit. psychosocial stages. While Morrison (2012: 221), describes the way that teachers can do in developing social emotional, namely Encouraging and supporting children's efforts to design, make things, and participate in learning about self-regulation and increasing the ability to control emotional and their behavior to build social relationships positive with others.

The finding of this research was supported by Meghan et al. (2009: 675), good teacher support and motivation are the main factors in educating children who have aggressive behavior, and developing positive behavior, providing motivation in building positive relationships with peers. While the research of Yan Lia et al (2015: 129), concluded that early childhood education teachers who understand the aspects of children's social emotional development well, the teacher easily teaches children to be able to adjust themselves to their social environment and influence social emotional development and reduce child behavior problems. Santrock (2008: 460), explains that there are several stimuli that can be done by teachers or parents for guidance on children's social emotional development, including: 1) Improve children 's self esteem. Can be refined by identifying the causes of low self esteem, providing emotional support and social approval and helping children's achievement. 2) Help children understand their emotion and cope with stress. When children can express their emotions stable, try to keep them from feeling stressed, and help children learn effectively strategically. 3) Nurture children's moral development. Parents can help their children with warm care rather than punishment, provide discipline and provide opportunities with children to learn about views in the family environment and social behavior. 4) create school that supports children 's social emotional development. Teachers not only provide good stimulation of children's cognitive development but also must know how children feel comfortable with themselves. 5) Improve childrens' peer and friend ship skills.

Peers and good friendships are very important to improve children's prosocial behavior. While the research results of Giacomo et al. (2013: 1978), concluded that the development of social emotional aspects in the development of children including developing self-regulation, self-control (social control), social ability, and building a harmonious relationship between peers . It can develop various aspects of child development including cognitive aspects, behavior, and emotional social abilities.

The great responsibility of the teacher as an educator who meets students every day indirectly requires the teacher to be able to master the social emotional learning model. These skills include character education, personality, 21st century skills, soft skills, and non-cognitive skills (Jones and Doolottle, 2017).

Positive support for children is the basis for their growth and development, children always construct their knowledge through interaction with their environment without pressure. Children who grow up with a cool atmosphere in their lives certainly have an output for child and mental stagnation high curiosity (inquiry).

Exemplary

The finding of research in Setia kindergarten are one strategy used by teachers to stimulate children's social emotional development through example. Exemplary method is a method of education / learning that is based on examples of behavior shown by parents and educators. In the context of early childhood education, exemplary methods can be demonstrated and carried out by an educator. Because, one of the characteristics and uniqueness of early childhood is to imitate (imitation) Albert Bandura (William Crain, 2014: 303). Therefore, when educators (parents, teachers) show good attitudes in their daily lives, especially in the learning process, students will automatically be observed and followed. children who always give role models in actions, sayings and attitudes, provide direction, and guidance in socialization.

The finding of this study are supported by Martsiswati & Suryono's Research (2012: 196), which shows that educators have an important role in applying discipline to develop good children's behavior. The teacher also provides a safe and comfortable atmosphere for children. The teacher establishes closeness with the child, and familiarizes the child with other children. In addition, for children who have difficulty in socializing the teacher approaches and collaborates with parents. According to Lickona (2013: 100), teachers can occupy positions as caregivers, moral models, and ethical counselors. Teachers should be fair, display examples and direct moral teaching, teach about moral values, honesty, and responsibility.

Thus the child will be able to develop his moral behavior well. The results of this study are also supported by research by Chan and Chou (2013: 1071) which shows that teachers who implement learning that are appropriate to children's abilities in social emotional development and other aspects by applying modeling, induction, and assigning tasks can develop good social emotional children .

The finding of this research were supported by Gregory et al. (2010: 602) concluded that the learning model provided by the teacher, and the curriculum that is appropriate to children's needs, good classroom conditions, teacher qualifications and various effective services can contribute well to children's social emotional development. While Ki Hadjar Dewantoro (Sujiono, 2009) proposed the concept of "Ingarso Sung tulodo, ingmadyo build kararso, tut wuri handayani". Teachers and parents should be role models, examples, exemplary before their children, always provide teaching and character guidance, parents are also motivators providing motivation, encouraging children to have a sense, creativity and intention in their lives. The teacher has an

important role in the child's social emotional learning process. Schools become a place of socialization for a child. Through children's school environment environmental norms will be introduced, also introduced norms of social life. In other words, in school a child will learn to behave, learn habits, values, norms, ways of thinking, acting, and imitating the teacher as an inspirational figure in the school environment. For a child the teacher is a role model that will be copied by a child. The existence of guidance and teaching from teachers which is considered a model for children will influence the social development of children.

Playing

Role playing is an important method in developing the six aspects of child development including social aspects of children. The world of children is the world of play. Play method is a method that applies certain games as children's learning. Symilaski (Sujiono, 2009) explains that play consists of repeated responses just for functional pleasure. The theory of psychoanalysis put forward by Freud (Suyanto, 2005: 116) playing is an emotional release device. While Erikson (Suyanto, 2005: 116) playing can also develop self-confidence, children's social abilities and express their feelings freely without inner pressure. Playing is done for fun, without considering the end result, done voluntarily and more driven by intricate factors. Playing has a function for children, namely: developing physical, cognitive, social-emotional, language and communication balance; live various experiences gained through everyday life; anticipate the role that children will play in the future; perfect various abilities through various physical, cognitive, social-emotional, language and communication skills, as well as the formation of positive behaviors. The results of this study are reinforced by Musyarofah research (2017), one method of stimulating social emotional development through role playing, so as to develop physical, cognitive, social-emotional, language and communication balance; live various experiences gained through everyday life; anticipate the role that children will play in the future; perfect various abilities through various physical, cognitive, social-emotional, language and communication skills, as well as the formation of positive behaviors. During play, children can play negative life experiences by dividing them into smaller parts, releasing the feelings that accompany each part, assimilating each experience back to the views they have about themselves, and gaining new levels of mastery (Homeyer and Morrison, 2008: 212)

In principle, early childhood learning is to use the principle of learning through play. So that learning media and game tools are arranged and provided so that it is fun, encouraging, and democratic in order to attract children to be involved in every learning activity. Through playing children can develop all areas of development, both physical motoric, language, intellectual, moral, social and emotional development of children.

The Role of Teachers in Early Childhood Education

From the previous data presentation, it is known that the teacher's role in developing the social emotional aspects of early childhood, the teacher acts as a role model, mentor, facilitator and motivates children's collective play activities, the teacher acts as a good leader for children who always give role models in actions, words and attitudes, giving direction, and guidance in socialization. The teacher also provides a safe and comfortable atmosphere for children. The teacher establishes closeness with the child, and familiarizes the child with other children. In addition, for children who have difficulty in socializing the teacher approaches and collaborates with parents.

The Finding of this research are supported by Ki Hadjar Dewantara's theory in Sudjiono (2009: 127) that in educating teachers should understand the concept as follows *Ing ngarso sung tulodo*, meaning if educators are in front of the mandatory to set an example for students applied to early childhood, educators in the front give good examples. Early children to be able to establish moral values can be instilled through modeling and habituation does not need many educators to give lectures. Insight builds *Ing madyo mangun karso*, meaning if educators are in in the middle of having to build more, encourage or motivate students' children, so that children can be creative themselves or independently. This among the systems is more precisely applied to children aged above kindergarten. *Tut Wuri Handayani*, meaning if the educator is in back must give encouragement, motivation and direction so that children can take a shower ri in doing the assignment. This among the systems required by educators to be able to understand it well. The teacher is in front, in the middle and also behind to set an example, guidance, and encouragement in educating children as a method of cultivation in children.

Efforts that can be made by the teacher to develop social aspects of early childhood according to Morrison (2012: 221), explain there are several ways that teachers can do in developing social emotional children including: 1) Give children the freedom to find out. 2) Give projects with activities that make it easier for children to find and experiment. 3) Encourage and support children's efforts to design, make things, and participate in learning about self-regulation and increasing the ability to control their emotional and behavioral behavior to build positive social relationships with others.

The teacher has an important role in the child's social learning process. Schools become a place of socialization for a child. The teacher will begin to include influences on child socialization. Children will be introduced to close environmental norms, also introduced norms of social life. In other words, at school a child will learn to behave, learn habits, values, norms, ways of thinking, acting, and so on from a teacher. The results of this study are also reinforced by Musyarofah (2017) research concluded that the teacher acts as a facilitator and motivates children's collective play activities, the teacher acts as a good leader for children who always give role models in actions, words and attitudes, provide direction, and guidance in children's social development .

Pestalozzi (Sujiono, 2009) argues that educators need to pay attention to 5 concepts in nurturing, guiding, and educating, namely: 1) heart, early childhood educators must teach sincerely, from the bottom of their hearts and not based on coercion. 2) Hand, the educator must have the skills to be creative so that the stimulation given to the child is appropriate, appropriate and interesting. 3) healthy, educators must be healthy physically and spiritually because someone's teaching will be very influential on the continuity of learning and life of children. 4) head, educators must have a broad mindset, so that it is expected that the insight of their students will increase. 5) Harmony educators must be able to make children safe, comfortable and enjoyable during the learning activities. For a child the teacher is a role model that will be copied by a child. The existence of guidance and teaching from teachers which is considered a model for children will influence the social development of children.

CONCLUSION

The emotional and social abilities of early childhood in Setia Baubau Kindergarten include: the ability to socialize, socialize and communicate with friends and teachers well, cooperate, be patient waiting for their turn, care and help friends who have difficulty doing assignments in class, sharing food and toys , succumbing to friends, being responsible, happy to play together, love each other, not easily angry, and empathetic. However, there are also children who have not developed their social emotional optimally. The method used in stimulating children's social emotional

development in Setia Baubau Kindergarten is: habituation, exemplary, developing children's self-confidence and playing.

The role of the teacher in stimulating the development of social emotional aspects of early childhood in Setia kindergarten of Baubau include: the teacher acts as a role model, mentor, facilitator and motivates children's collective play activities, the teacher acts as a good leader for children who always give role models in actions, speech and attitude, giving direction, and guidance in socialization and emotional settings of children. The teacher also provides a safe and comfortable atmosphere for children, establishes closeness with children, and familiarizes children with other children. In addition, for children who experience difficulties in socializing and emotionally unstable the teacher approaches and collaborates with parents in developing social attitudes and emotional settings of children. Referring to the 2013 curriculum legislation that in the learning process, the teacher is not fully responsible to the students, but parents and the community environment take part in shaping this attitude.

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